

DIRECTIONS AND METHODS OF TEACHING TYPES OF CREATIVE WRITING TO STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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"Writing is one of the most valuable parts of language that allows students to freely express their thoughts and feelings. It is a complex and lengthy process that involves writing; a skill that contributes to individuals in any academic activity to plan, design, review and re-evaluate, explain ideas and combine them to form an appropriately meaningful sentence"¹. Writing is a skill-intensive process, so it's important to create a perfect set of methods for teaching it.

The methodology of foreign language teaching as a science has more than 200 years of history. During this period, it can be observed that different attitudes towards foreign language teaching methods were expressed. One of these views belongs to academician L.V. Shcherba. In his opinion, although the teaching methodology of any subject is a science, it is not considered a theoretical science. It solves practical problems. In particular, the methodology of foreign language teaching does not rely only on the evidence of psychology, but is based on general and specific linguistic studies. If linguistics deals with the origin and laws of movement of language phenomena, the methodology answers the question of what should be done in order to use the necessary language phenomenon in practice based on these laws. The most valuable books on methodology are also written by linguists. These include G. Suit, one of the 19th century phoneticians and a great

¹ Richards, J. C. & Schmidt, R. (2002). Language Teaching and Applied Linguistics. Edinburgh: Pearson Education Limited.

English linguist, O. Yespersen, who is considered the most original phonetician and theoretical linguist in England at the end of the 19th and early 20th centuries, and one of the most prominent French linguists in the late 19th and early 20th centuries, F. .Bryuns and Brealya, prominent anglicist and famous phonetician V. Fyotor and others. Academician L.V. Shcherba and his mentor, the great linguist scientist I.A. Baudouin-de-Courtone and their students dealt with the issue of language teaching methodology in Russia. Psychologists have a different attitude to the methodology of foreign language teaching.

Professor V.A. Artemov gave a valuable opinion about the relationship between methodology and psychology. In his opinion, psychology provides material for methodology. Methodology studies how a teacher conducts a lesson. Psychology deals with how students master this subject. However, one cannot fully agree with this opinion. Because the teacher in the process of teaching, and the student in the period of mastering, experience certain mental processes and states, whether they want to or not, they face and are influenced by the laws of psychology.

A deeper study of the literature on the history of methodology shows that some researchers call methodology an art. They usually refer to the idea of the French Methodist Penlache, that there are no "good" or "bad" methods, only "good" or "bad" teachers. People who have such an opinion can be answered with the thoughts of the German Methodist E. Otto, expressed in 1924. He says: "If someone considers methodology to be an art, he confuses the theory of science with its practical application."

Each discipline has its own set of concepts. Among the main concepts adopted in the foreign language teaching methodology, the following can be included: educational system, educational method, educational principle, educational tool, methodological method.

The method of teaching a foreign language means the set of activities of the teacher and the student that ensure the achievement of the practical, general

educational, educational and developmental goals of teaching a foreign language. The term method is used in the sense of "set of educational methods" and "direction of education". First, in the theory of education, the process is used in the sense of methods, and in the second sense, we can find it in works on the history of teaching methods. For example, translation method, correct method, conscious-comparative method, traditional method, intensive method, etc. are considered as foreign language teaching methods.

Nikolay Vasilievich Baryshkinov emphasized that in teaching a foreign language, "Students should act at an individual speed corresponding to the speed of learning the material."² So, after conducting psycholinguistic and linguodidactic analyzes in foreign language teaching, it is appropriate to choose directions and methods based on the state of learning of students. Among the students of higher education institutions, especially those whose main subject is English, the knowledge level of most of them is CEFR level B2 and C1, the age range is 18-23 years old, because they can learn well by watching and doing exercises. We have identified the following directions and methods for developing creative writing skills.

"Developing writing skills gives a person many advantages in life. Some of these advantages are the ability to develop memory and retain information, the ability to express one's opinion comfortably, to encourage a person to communicate, to develop the ability to reason and to have the ability to make logical and convincing arguments."³

Creative writing is defined as a skill that enables students to understand and learn about the value and functions of writing and contributes to the development of students' reading and writing skills.

² Барышников Н.В. Методика обучения второму иностранному языку в школе. –М., 2003. 159с

³ Klimova, F. B. (2014). Detecting the development of language skills in current English language teaching in the Czech Republic. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 158, 85-92.

Creative writing is an achievement that goes beyond accepted values, it is rare and beyond the cliché, and it is the ability to use only one's imagination to come up with different ideas. will be carried out by those who came up with it"⁴.

“While creative writing is an individual skill, it's limited to those who don't have it because it's a skill that requires being a good reader. Therefore, in order to develop creative writing skills, it is necessary to ensure that individuals think differently. In addition, they should be encouraged to write unique texts and develop problem-solving skills on topics they have not encountered before, and to read on a variety of topics to develop creative writing skills.”⁵

It is observed that students with advanced creative writing skills have a higher level of mastery of languages such as grammar and vocabulary compared to other students. Students' vocabulary can be defined as knowing the meanings of written and spoken words. Knowing more words allows us to better understand and listen to what we read. It also allows us to express ourselves better in speaking and writing.

Some studies in different regions have found that narrative and informational texts written by high school students with sufficient vocabulary are of high quality.⁶In addition, Olinghouse and Laird noted in their research that vocabulary diversity plays an important role in meaningful narrative writing skills in second and fourth grades. In addition, vocabulary plays a key role in ensuring active use of language in writing.

When the relevant literature was studied, it was observed that students-young people with creative writing skills have writing skills, having sufficient vocabulary and writing high-quality stories in terms of meaning.

Although it is not prescribed by the curriculum of higher education institutions for foreign language and literature students, we believe that the creative writing

⁴ Küçük, S. (2007). *Yazılı Anlatım ve Yaratıcılık*. Samsun: On Dokuz Mayıs Üniversitesi Yayınları.

⁵ Akkaya, N. (2014). Elementary teachers' views on the creative writing process: An evaluation. *Educational Sciences: Theory and Practice*, 14(4), 1499-1504.

⁶ Olinghouse, N. G. & Laird, J. T. (2009). The relationship between measures of vocabulary and narrative writing quality in second- and fourth-grade students. *Reading and Writing*, 22, 545–565.

module is necessary, especially for the preparation of highly qualified students. The experience of teaching creative writing in recent years has shown that creative writers usually emphasize fiction or poetry. To meet their needs, we have chosen to include creative writing tasks in literature, culture and other social studies classes by organizing workshops to strengthen students' writing skills and techniques. The types of creative writing that work best with students are short stories, novels, poems, autobiographies, personal and journalistic essays.

"Since any type of writing must have a self-declared purpose, we can assign creative writing primarily to meet the following needs:

1. 1. the need to record important experience;
2. 2. the need to share factual experience and personal relationships;
3. 3. the need for free individual expression."⁷

It's also helpful to remember the many things we can use writing for. For example, regardless of the students' level of knowledge, most of us use writing to make a note of something, to record what we want to remember; we text and text our friends, and some of us keep a journal. Most of us have to fill out forms like applications and questionnaires from time to time and occasionally we write official letters like complaints, inquiries, job applications. Also, the amount of writing we do on a regular basis depends on our professional life. As any profession is unique, most students spend a lot of time writing letters, instructions, memos, and reports. Few of us, on the other hand, can spend time writing poetry or fiction.⁸

Since applications, questionnaires, letters, and other such writings are written in a formal style, the grammar and vocabulary used in them should also be formal. When teaching students this type of writing, it is important to teach them to distinguish words used in formal style from words used in everyday life.

⁷ Mary Lee Marksberry, *Foundation of Creativity*, Harper's Series on Teaching, London: Harper & Row, 2003, 39.

⁸ Donn Byrne, *Teaching Writing Skills*, London and New York, Longman, 2005, 2.

"To write an official letter, first of all, you need to understand the reason for the letter. The structure of the letter varies depending on the type of letter. There are certain rules that must be followed in order to compose an official letter. Each sentence should be carefully thought out and written in such a way that the intended message is clear and understandable to the reader.

There are different types of formal letters and they can generally be defined under the following conditions:

- Business letters
- Application letters
- Letters to newspapers

Professional letters should be short, clear and to the point. There is no place for any kind of story in a business letter. Before you start writing your professional letter, here are some things to consider:

- a) Use simple, everyday language instead of using vocabulary that is obvious and overemphasizes the message.
- b) Never use common business jargon when writing a business letter.
- c) Avoid using abbreviations as much as possible.
- d) Addressing methods vary depending on the type of letter and recipient.
- e) When writing to order goods, precise and accurate descriptions of the goods required with the expected quality and quantity should be very carefully listed.
- f) When replying to a business letter, always quote the date of the reply letter and its reference numbers (if applicable).
- g) Official/business letters include letters from the employer to employees and vice versa, ordering and exchanging goods, letters of serious concern to a senior official, letters of complaint, etc.

Before and after writing a letter of application, you should pay attention to the following:

a) Always start with a short introduction that indicates the applicant is responding to an advertisement found online or in a newspaper.

b) indicate the age, education and experience of the applicant.

c) provide the employer with a genuine representation of the applicant's seriousness in applying for a job in the relevant company.

d) also provide references so that the employer can gather an idea of what kind of employee you would be.

e) Application letters should follow the format of formal/business letters.

Letters to newspapers

Always send such letters to the "Editor" and end with the phrase "Sincerely."

Letters to the editor are letters that raise issues that need to be addressed to higher authorities. These letters should be professional and authentic. No newspaper will publish anonymous letters, so make sure the letter is being written for a reason and that the name and address are correct.

When writing a formal letter, always be respectful of your language, regardless of the subject of the letter. There are some points to keep in mind when writing a formal letter.

1. Always start with the sender's address

2. It comes after the date.

3. The recipient's address follows. The recipient can be a company name or a company representative.

4. The subject of the letter is very important. This is to state the purpose of the letter. It should be written on one line.

5. Hello Dear Sir/Madam. If the person you are contacting is someone you know well, say "Dear... you can apply with first or last name.

6. The main part of the letter can be written in 3 paragraphs.

7. The first paragraph should focus on introducing yourself and stating the purpose of your letter.

8. The second paragraph should contain all the information on this issue.

9. The third paragraph can be the final paragraph in which you state your assumptions about the issue.

10. To close the letter, you can use additional endings such as "Sincerely", "Sincerely", etc.

Unlike informal letters, a signature should include your name (in capital letters) and your signature.

Basic techniques of essay writing:

An essay should have a beginning, middle, and end. The introduction should describe the problem, explain why it is important, and summarize the main arguments. It's boring to start with a dictionary definition. It should summarize the main arguments in the middle and conclude with conclusions that answer the essay question.

Good essay writing technique means having a well organized essay. The essay should be based on a plan. Creating a bulleted list, table, or spider diagram with the key components of the answer will help you sort them out clearly. Poor structure is one of the main reasons why students get low marks on essays. It is important to organize ideas logically and follow the essay plan.

The main thing the examiners are looking for is to see that you understand the question. The student should be able to demonstrate conceptual awareness and understanding of key issues. Clear and illustrated with examples relevant to the work and topic. Figures or pictures or maps can be used to illustrate an idea. Regular reading of books makes the written essay rich and colorful, and the student should express this perfectly in the essay.

To make sure the student answers the question, if it's a compare and contrast question, they'll need to show both sides of the argument. If it's a "clarify and explain" type of question, you'll need to demonstrate a deep understanding of the topic. If it consists of two parts, the essay is divided into two parts to answer the

question. Reading the topic thoroughly before you start is a sign that you're halfway there.⁹

In conclusions, the student should summarize his arguments. No new items are introduced at this stage. The most important points are highlighted and the final conclusion is given.

When writing an essay, grammar, lexis and the interrelationship of the text in terms of structure and content are also important.

The following activities are used as building blocks to improve student writing and as tools to help teach creative writing skills. Once learned, these activities serve as tools for students to continue with in future writing activities.

1. Students are shown how to use graphic organizers such as story maps to help them think before they start writing. A story map is a tool often used in teaching reading and writing to help learners understand important elements of a story. Before starting a story, students are asked to plan story elements such as character, plot, setting, theme, problem, and solution on a story map so they can refer to it when writing the story. First, the teacher fills out a graphic organizer with students to make it understandable and helps them come up with story elements that should be in the organizer.

2. Reading to students, regardless of their age, helps them develop a vision of what high-quality writing should look like. Before reading a book or sample, introduce a specific feature of writing, such as choosing words, phrases, and expressions that match the topic, and then ask students to listen to the samples as they read from the book. This method helps students to later imitate the characteristic of the book or text they read in their creative writing, perfecting it when they create a new text.

3. Writing poetry is considered a separate art, it requires a special talent from a person to write it, and teaching this activity to students is also a difficult task. But

⁹ [Essay Writing Technique \(antarcticglaciers.org\)](http://antarcticglaciers.org)

if students are taught the technique of writing short poems, they will be able to do this task easily. For this, it is necessary to analyze the poems written using the a-b-a-b rhyming or a-a-a-a rhyming structure and find rhyming words. To stimulate interest, use interesting poems by poets and writers such as children's author and poet Dr. Seuss or Shel Silverstein. As students gain confidence, it is appropriate to teach them about a longer, more complex poem.

4. Writing a letter. Considering the age of the students, they like to write notes, diaries during this period, so making it formal and teaching the students to write a proper letter will give the expected result.